

Is Life Chemical or Physical in Origin?*

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One of the problems of biophysics is to understand the scientific causes for the differences between animate and inanimate matter, if any. We first consider the geometries of life (logarithmic spirals; fractals) and symmetries. These suggest that life is not random, but orderly. We present theoretical evidence (calculations) and experimental evidence (DNA palindromes) that *DNA did not evolve by random mutations*. We deduce that there needs to be source(s) of order in nature. We consider briefly a number of theories of life, including those based upon self-organisation and systems theory, various biological approaches and physics. We note Szent-Györgyi's criticisms of molecular biology, that as one descends from higher levels to lower (via organs, cells, molecules) one is left empty-handed because proteins outside cells are lifeless. We present evidence that water is essential for life, and in addition that life at the smallest scales appears to be *physical* (heavy water is poisonous). However, none of these theories supply the order required. We present a preliminary physics theory of the food chain, which shows that sunlight creates order on the earth's surface, which can be captured and stored by photosynthesis. But what happened before photosynthesis developed? Either chlorophyll developed by random chemical processes, OR there is some mechanism in physics for capturing and storing the order produced by sunlight, to facilitate the generation of more complex states. If such a storage mechanism exists then life is physical, if not then it is chemical in origin.

Keywords: Evolution by random mutations; DNA Palindromes; Geometry and symmetry; Animate versus inanimate; Sunlight creates order; chemical versus physical origin of life.

I. INTRODUCTION

In order to read this and understand it, your brain has to be alive. In fact it has to be alive to do science. But we do not know for sure, what life is, nor how it works. This is not a simple problem, because the brain is the central instrument of biology, and so this has many ramifications. For example, we don't know how the brain works, so we don't know whether it introduces any

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bias into our scientific research. For example does the brain think that if it can control something, then it understands it? We don't even know if the human brain is capable of understanding other living organisms correctly, if it does not understand the life processes in itself. At its core, we don't even know if the brain has evolved correctly so that we can find the truth in nature. In fact, we don't even know for sure that it evolved. Where is the survival value in being able to do advanced mathematics and build machines to detect gravitational waves from colliding black holes?[1]

II. EVOLUTION

Yet evolution has been central to biology since Darwin and this continued through the twentieth century in the modern synthesis. If we go back to Darwin, it is important to remember that he did not see his theory of evolution as being a theory of life. For example, in a letter to Sir J. Hooker, he wrote *It is mere rubbish thinking at present of the origin of life; one might as well think of the origin of matter.*[2] Then was then. Now physicists have discovered the Higgs boson, which creates mass.[3] So perhaps we should try to understand life.

According to Darwin, life started aeons ago, and evolved slowly by natural selection into its present complex states we observe. In the 20th century, natural selection and Mendelian genetics were brought together in the modern synthesis, which its founders each defined slightly differently. But at its core, all versions included natural selection acting on heritable variation, supplied by mutation. It is this synthesis which has now started to break down.

This modern synthesis, whereby random changes in DNA would lead to evolution by natural selection,[4] was quite plausible. So this started to become a theory of life, with DNA at the centre of it, both for biochemists and for the popular scientific mind. For example, a (physics) colleague at CERN once said to me "Living organisms are random collections of chemicals which have evolved by chance on the earth's surface".[5] The problem is that this is not possible and is also contrary to the facts, as we shall see.

Note the use of the word 'chance'. 'Chance' is an ambiguous word - it signifies a statistical process without specifying whether it is correlated or random. That is to say, it does not specify whether some outcomes are more likely than others (peaked probability distribution, i.e. the dice are loaded), or whether all outcomes are equally likely (flat probability distribution) which is true randomness. The point is that if the correlation is strong enough, then the outcome is sufficiently certain that it is not random. The calculations in later sections assume that the probability distribution is flat and so truly random.

III. THE GEOMETRIES OF LIFE

The idea of randomness (eg random mutations) has just slipped into the picture above as if it is something quite certain. But is it? Where is the proof? Randomness came into medicine in the 19th century. This upset the physiologist Claude Bernard, who thought that statistical methods were inappropriate for science.[6] His approach was to cut a nerve, see what dysfunction occurred, and then reconnect that nerve and show the function had been restored. For him this was real science. However, living organisms are very complex, and the assumption that they are random in origin persisted, and then found its way into the modern synthesis. Let us examine the geometries of living organisms, to see if we can find evidence for this randomness.

Botany is very much concerned with the physical properties of plants and flowers. The botanical descriptions of plants involve mainly geometry and colour, both of which are physical properties. *Plants are not identified by chemical tests*, but by the geometrical shapes and colours of their stems, leaves and flowers. We now present more detailed evidence that plants (and some other organisms) are a geometrical physical phenomena.

A. Geometries of Growth

As living organisms grow, their cells divide and create new cells, which in turn divide and grow. These iterative processes give rise to several geometries of growth:

A. Logarithmic Spirals The shells of snails and certain sea shells such as abalone (*Haliotis Parvus*) show a spiral line of growth. Sunflower heads (*Helianthus maximus*) show spiral lines of growth in the florets. The potentially infinite sequence of chambers in *Nautilus* obeys a discrete group of dilations in a geometrical progression (s^n , where s is a fraction and $n = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \pm 3, \dots$). There are various other sea shells (eg *Triton Tritonis* and *Turritella duplicata*) which display logarithmic spirals of growth.

B. Fibonacci Series In 1202 Fibonacci, whose real name was Leonardo of Pisa, published his mathematical series, which was the solution to the problem of how many rabbits would be produced by a single pair after one year. For example if a pair of rabbits do not produce any offspring for first two months, and then produce two rabbits each month thereafter, then the numbers of pairs of rabbits increases as follows: 1, 1, 2, 3, 5, 8, 13, 21, 34, 55, 89, 144.[7] Note that each term is the sum of the preceding two terms. The ratio of any two adjacent terms tends asymptotically to $\Phi = 1.618\dots$ A series of rectangles with sides having this ratio, can be used to construct logarithmic

spirals, which are found in abalone and other sea shells. The spiral based on the ratio $\sqrt{\Phi}$ is characteristic of the beautiful shell *Dolium pernix*. Other shells such as *Murex*, *Fusus Antiquus*, *Scalaria pretiosa*, *Solarium trochleare* and many ammonites are based on $\Phi^{1/4}$.

The growth section Φ has a number of unusual mathematical properties. For example $\Phi^2 = \Phi + 1$; also $1/\Phi = \Phi - 1$; and $\Phi = (\sqrt{5} + 1)/2$. It is this last equation which links growth to the number five. This could explain why pentagonal shapes and symmetry are quite common in nature - see below. The logarithmic growth spiral and the pentagon appear to be quite different, but they are in fact related mathematically in this way.

C. The Geometry of Buds In the 1970s, Edwards noted that most flower buds have precise geometrical shapes, despite their apparent diversity. He found that their profiles closely resembled W-curves, which were first described by Klein and Lie in 1870. Edwards did a statistical analysis of the profiles of the buds of 125 different species, and found that 80% were closely fitted by W-curves. Lacroix has suggested that W-curves are trajectories or orbits of a point moving in a plane, and so they are another kind of growth curve.[8] These geometrical forms are not random.

B. Symmetry

Many animals have left-right symmetry. Physicists use the word "symmetry" in a technical sense to refer to the mathematical procedure to transform an object into itself. For example, your right hand is the mirror image of your left hand. Symmetry implies mathematical order, whereas randomness does not.

There are various kinds of symmetry found in living organisms, in addition to the DNA palindromes discussed below. A simple type of translational symmetry is *linear*. This is found in bamboo, which is approximately the same as one moves from one knot to the next. Plants with long pinnate leaves, such as *Angraecum distichum*, have linear translational symmetry. Certain small animals, such as a *scolopendrid*, which has many legs like a millipede, also displays linear translational symmetry.

Rotational symmetry is of greater interest. This is found when you rotate an object a certain amount and it is the same. For example, if you rotate an equilateral triangle by 120° it looks the same. A square has to be rotated 90° and a pentagon by 72° . An iris flower has three-fold (120°) rotational symmetry. *Veronica officinalis* (speedwell) flowers have a four-fold symmetry. *Hoya Carnosa* (wax plant), *Anagallis arvensis* (scarlet pimpernel) and many other flowers, such as fruit blossoms, primroses, passion flowers, have a five-fold symmetry. In particular, *Hoya carnososa* has

sprays of pentagonal shaped flowers. Pentagonal symmetry is found in many marine organisms, including star fishes and sea-urchins, and in a number of smaller marine organisms. This is possibly due to the relationship between growth processes and the number 5, shown above.

Bellis perennis (daisy) has an n-fold circular symmetry because it has so many identical petals in a circle. *Medusa* (jellyfish) also display marked circular symmetry. Thompson in his classic work says *the living medusa has geometrical symmetry so marked and regular as to suggest a physical or mechanical element in the little creature's growth and construction.*[9]

Related to these rotational symmetries, are the symmetries of regular polyhedra. In three dimensions, there are only five regular polyhedra. These are the Platonic solids: the tetrahedron, the octahedron, the cube, the icosahedron and the dodecahedron. Jaeger notes that the shapes of all five regular solids are found in the skeletons of protozoa (radiolarians).[10] For example the icosahedron is found in *Circogonia icosahedra*, and the dodecahedron in *Circorhegma dodecahedra*. [11] The cells of various plant seeds also roughly resemble the Platonic solids.

There are many other examples of symmetries in living organisms. Most living creatures have left-right symmetry. Many organisms have beautiful symmetrical markings - the tail of the peacock, the markings of birds and butterflies, and so on. This is evidence on the macroscopic level that living organisms are not random.

This evidence for mathematical symmetry and the Platonic solids in living organisms, is much more significant than non-physicists might think. Physicists consider symmetry to be a deep fundamental principle of nature. In fact it is at the heart of physics. Physicists have deliberately sought out the fundamental symmetries of nature in order to build the modern theories of physics upon them. *If life was random, there would be no symmetries in living organisms.* Thus the symmetries noted above, are evidence for deep *mathematical* order underlying living organisms.

C. Fractal Geometry

Despite the above evidence for logarithmic spirals and symmetry, the idea that living organisms are random persisted. For example, if you go into a rain forest, everything seems to sprout up at random. Furthermore, the geometry of living organisms is not Euclidian. So if you think a geometrically well ordered form should be like a Greek temple, then this is not found in living organisms. As a result, their geometry appears to be random, at least when compared to that of Euclid, which was the standard geometry in the 19th century. However, since then there have been major developments in the mathematics of different geometries. Now there is a new type, fractal

geometry, which is the geometry of natural processes and living organisms.

Fractal geometry was introduced by Benoit Mandelbrot in 1975. It built upon research in different branches of mathematics, to create a whole new field of geometry that can represent natural shapes, such as coastlines, clouds, mountains, lightning, and plants such as ferns, broccoli and living organisms. F.J. Dyson has given an eloquent summary.[12] Fractal geometry is built upon repeating patterns, and is now used widely in physics, biology, anatomy, and other sciences. The small amount written here does not do justice to the subject, and the reader is referred to books and other references.

A rough definition of a fractal is that it is something that has a repeating pattern that is found on different scales from small to large, and which may or may not have the property of fractional dimension. Fractals are constructed according to a systematic set of rules. When the rules are followed precisely, *randomness is excluded*. Fractal patterns may appear random, but if the rules are followed precisely, *they have their own fractal determinism* and are different from randomness. Computers have been used to perform the repetitive calculations necessary to create complex fractal patterns.

It has been found that fractals can be used to model natural landscapes and living organisms quite accurately. In fact, there is a new technology of fractal communication. This enables pictures of landscapes, including animals and humans, to be reduced to fractal equations, *without randomness*. These equations can then be transmitted to another computer and the original picture reconstructed from these equations with high quality.[13]

Fractal anatomy is the study and analysis of living tissues using fractal geometry. Fractal structures are found in the airways in the lungs, in the nerves, in the neurons, in the blood vessels and in ducts throughout the body.[14] In fact the fractal geometry of the veins and arteries is quite subtle, so as to provide the maximum coverage of the body for the minimum amount of blood. Mandelbrot has gone into this in some detail.[15]

Fractals are a set of rules for creating larger, more complex structures out of simple shapes by repetition. So they lend themselves to describing growth processes. The complexity of growth processes which transform a seed into a tree or an egg into an animal, is beyond comprehension and defies traditional mathematical descriptions. Kaandorp has used fractal geometry to model the growth processes of certain corals and sponges.[16] He used computer techniques in which growth was simulated using fractal rules, with or without randomness, and compared the results with actual organisms. His model was quite sophisticated and allowed for various environmental factors such as: the supply of nutrients, salinity, temperature, or the motion of the water around

the corals or sponges. He found that the growth processes can be described by fractals, *without randomness*. Randomness only crept in as a result of contingency, such as necessary reaction to external events (e.g. contact with an external object). But the actual growth of sponges and corals takes place according to *fractal determinism*.

So living organisms have geometrical form. However, it is not Euclidean but fractal. So the idea that living organisms are random, appears not to be correct. We now turn to calculations to investigate this further.

IV. THE MODERN SYNTHESIS AND RANDOMNESS

Have living organisms evolved by random mutations? We first investigate this theoretically, then experimentally in a later section. Living organisms are very complex and highly ordered. For example, Murray has calculated that the information content per gram of living tissue is 10^{16} times greater than any computer technology known in 1990.[17] Whilst computer technology has progressed by one or a few orders of magnitude since then, nevertheless, living tissues still contain vastly higher densities of information than machines. Could this ultra-high level of order have originated by random processes?

A. Evolution and Randomness

We now present a simple calculation which suggests that the Universe is not old enough for a simple protein, with a specific sequence of say 100 amino acids, to have evolved by random processes. The number of permutations necessary to produce this specific sequence of 100 amino acids (there are 20 different types) is:

$$N \simeq 20^{100} \simeq 10^{130} \tag{1}$$

If we assume that all the configurations of this protein are equally probable a priori (i.e. a flat probability distribution), and that the initial structure changes every 10^{-8} seconds, which is faster than these biochemical changes would normally occur, then the time for the desired protein to form would be $t \simeq 10^{115}$ years. Given that the known age of the Universe is (only) about 10^{10} years, this suggests that this simple protein could not have arisen by random processes within the known age of the Universe.[18] This basically rules out random evolution as the origin of proteins, because the Universe is not old enough by a factor of 10^{105} (or more for more complex proteins).

There is an additional problem, because there is a window of less than 10^{-8} seconds (in 10^{115} years which is about 10^{122} seconds) for the protein to stop evolving and assume its stable form! It seems essentially impossible for natural selection to take place in such a short time. We suggest this be called the "microscopic time selection window". There are also problems defining natural selection - see below.

In addition, there is a problem arising from these two time scales, namely the "deep" time of evolution and the sub-second, even sub-microsecond, time scales of biochemistry. The problem is that it is not credible that something which happened millions or billions of years ago can control random processes (eg quantum fluctuations, thermal motions) in the present moment, unless there is something hidden which provides the control and makes the required things happen. Without this, there is no causality.

In discussions with scientists in my family, it was argued that in a large primaevial "soup", such processes could be going on in parallel in many places, and this would increase the probability of such a protein forming.[19] Assuming there are many planets with oceans like the earth's, then we calculate it would take 10^{64} such planets to produce one such small protein within the known age of the Universe. And then the next protein would form somewhere else on another planet. Thus a complex cell would never form in this way.

This calculation has been repeated in a different way. Hoyle and Wickramasinghe have shown that a simple cell of 2000 proteins could not have evolved by random processes, even if the *whole Universe*, including all of space, was filled with primaevial soup.[20] Thus living organisms are *far too complex* to have evolved from some primaevial soup, just by random chance. *Therefore, on the basis of this evidence, there has to be something which creates order out of chaos.*

B. Natural Selection

The reasoning above is that of physicists and is theoretical. Now let us consider how biologists view this. For example, Dawkins has attempted to solve this problem as follows.[21] He writes:

Astrophysicist Professor Chandra Wickramasinghe, has quoted him (Hoyle) as saying that spontaneous formation by 'chance' of a working enzyme is like a hurricane blowing through a junkyard and spontaneously having the luck to put together a Boeing 747. What Hoyle and Wickramasinghe miss is that Darwinism is not a theory of random chance. It is a theory of random mutation plus *non-random* cumulative natural selection.

So Dawkins assumes that natural selection can be defined scientifically, and that it somehow magically smooths out the randomness. However, Lima-de-Faria maintains that natural selection cannot be defined scientifically.[22] Certainly there is the problem, noted above, of the microscopic time selection window. If we ignore this for the moment, then given that mutations are random and that most mutations don't lead to positive heritable traits, it follows that most mutations will die out. This is a direct consequence of the randomness of mutations, and so the negative side of natural selection is random. The idea that the positive side of natural selection, which is the smallest part, is not random, is clearly wrong, because it also comes from random mutations - it is just that these are the "lucky" mutations.

The important point is that natural selection occurs *after the mutation*, and so cannot modify the probability. *Therefore all the failed mutations have to be experienced, and they should show up in the fossil record.* But there does not appear to be much evidence for this. In fact the fossils of failed mutations should far exceed the number of successful ones. The only way to avoid this conclusion is if natural selection has some kind of spooky ability to see into the future and select the "lucky" mutations in advance and thereby avoid the "unlucky" ones - but then this would not be scientific.

Secondly Dawkins likens the vast improbability of complex life forms to a mountain, and accuses the physicists of trying to leap up the North face of the Eiger, so to speak, whilst on the other side of this Mount Improbable, are gentle sloping lush meadows, which living organisms can slowly evolve upwards over aeons of time. In this way, they can evolve to the highest levels of complexity in small steps. The problem is that if the Universe is not old enough for a simple protein of 100 amino acids to have evolved by random means at the rapid rate of one mutation every 10^{-8} seconds, *then it is very definitely not old enough for more complex organisms to have evolved more slowly up the South face, whether through all those lush alpine meadows or not.*

Thirdly he points out that all living organisms have ancestors who survived long enough to reproduce, and therefore they include the "lucky" genes of their ancestors, a sort of collective ancestral wisdom. This really takes us to the heart of the problem, which is that *physicists and biologists are talking about two different things. Physicists want to understand the difference between lifeless and living matter (which is the focus of this paper), whilst evolutionary biologists are content to study the subtle changes which lead existing living organisms to evolve into new species.* As a result, Darwin's theory is not a theory of life and he admitted this. Unfortunately some of his followers do not. The problem is that they mistake the facade (e.g. the biochemicals) for the deeper truth probably hidden behind the facade.

C. Replicators

For example, Dawkins asserts that we are all Total Replication Instruction Programs (TRIPs) or von Neumann machines, that is robots without life, with just the ability to replicate. He attempts to explain the origin of life as follows. He speculates that some primaevial soup of organic molecules formed aeons ago. Then, without violating the laws of physics or chemistry, a molecule formed which was self-copying - *a replicator*. The problem is that before it formed it was not alive, *and so natural selection does not apply*. Therefore the process is definitely random and the above method of calculation (see equation 1) applies. Therefore the likelihood of a simple protein so forming is negligible, unless it was so simple as to be trivial, and so not capable of replicating. And even if it did so form and replicate, it could not climb this impossible probability mountain (and so become the complexity we observe) within the known age of the Universe. Thus Dawkins' attempt to explain the origin of life is defeated by the physics calculation he set out to disprove by writing the book. The problem is that randomness is a real problem - Hoyle was right.

The problem is that life as we know it, could not have come into existence by random processes, nor could it have evolved to the complex forms we see around us, within the known age of the earth, unless you give natural selection some kind of spooky powers to see into the future. This theory is a bit like saying that to earn a living all you have to do is win the lottery and live off the money. When that runs out, just win the lottery again. Clearly this is impossible - yet the odds of winning the lottery are much better than those for the random evolution of even a simple protein. Therefore we need a source of order and an explanation for life.

We are thus back to the conclusion, that evolution by random processes could not have occurred within the known age of the Universe. But this is based upon theoretical reasoning (i.e. the calculation above). In the interest of science, does the experimental evidence support this? Firstly it predicts that the fossil record would contain the remains of failed mutations, which are likely to out-number those of successful mutations. There is evidence for organisms which have died out, but the evidence is that they were successful in their day. That is not the evidence we refer too. The evidence for failed mutations would consist of three-legged, or asymmetric, or deformed, or otherwise defective organisms due to failed mutations. But there is little or no evidence for these. Secondly, the modern synthesis asserts that DNA evolves by random mutations. *Therefore DNA should be random*. We can test this experimentally as follows.

Table 1: A symmetrical sequence of base-pairs in the lactose operator of *E. coli* DNA. The boxed region reads the same forwards as backwards and therefore is a palindrome.

T	G	G	AATTGT	G	A	G	C	G	G	A	T	A	ACAATT
A	C	C	TTAACA	C	T	C	G	C	C	T	A	T	TGTTAA

D. DNA Evidence

If the genetic code has evolved by random mutations, *then DNA should be random*. However, experimentally there are ordered patterns in DNA in the form of palindromes. A normal palindrome is a sequence of letters or words such as "madam" or "Able was I ere I saw Elba", which reads the same forwards and backwards. However DNA has two strands, and so most DNA palindromes have a nucleic-acid sequence reading one way, which is the same as that on the complementary strand, when read the reverse way. An example of this double-stranded mirror symmetry is shown in table 1. Palindromes are not random, but symmetrical and orderly. Thus these symmetrical patterns in the DNA are of profound significance.

The author first learned of palindromes in DNA when Lima-de-Faria, a molecular geneticist from the University of Lund, gave a colloquium at CERN in 1982, at the time of publishing his book on molecular evolution of the chromosome.[23] He explained that he had made a study of 25,000 papers in molecular genetics, looking for evidence for either order or disorder in the genetic code. He did not specifically look for order, but found evidence for order on most levels of the genetic code, in particular for symmetric patterns in the DNA. The ones which made the most impression on the present author are palindromes. Lima-de-Faria stated that they play significant roles in gene expression and regulation. He said that some of them are like labels, and that any random sequence could have been used, provided it was used consistently. Instead nature has chosen (mainly) symmetrical palindromes, and they are too large and too many of them to have arisen by random processes. Therefore he said. this calls for new physics (to create this order).

Recent evidence confirms this. For example, a survey of the 1000 Genomes database of human genetic variation, found $\simeq 10^7$ palindromes up to 40 base pairs long, and 182k palindromes longer than 40 bp. Of these, 783 are 100-200 bp long, and 718 are longer than 200 bp.[24] The number of permutations of 4 bases to produce 200 bp is $N \simeq 4^{200} \simeq 10^{120}$, which could not have arisen by random processes within the known age of the Universe. And this is just one of 718 longer palindromes! Even the shorter ones, except for the very shortest, are too improbable to have evolved by random mutations. It is important to note that palindromes are a widespread phenomena not

only for high eukaryotes, but also in protozoa.[25]

Ganapathiraju et. al. state that palindromes, which are distributed throughout the human genome, play a key role in gene regulation and expression.[24] Furthermore they find mutated palindromes are linked to many human diseases. They use sophisticated computer software and hardware to map all the palindromes and near-palindromes of the 2504 (mainly healthy) individuals in the 1000G database. They find that about 30% of the palindromes show variation. In particular they examine palindromes where one base has changed (single-nucleotide polymorphisms or SNPs). As a reference, they used a genome-wide association study (GWAS) Catalogue of SNPs that are associated statistically with specific diseases.[26] They found that disease-causing GWAS SNPs were 14 times more likely to occur in palindromic regions than expected. These imperfect palindrome variants were associated with diseases such as diabetes, obesity, Alzheimer's, attention deficit hyperactivity disorder, schizophrenia, Crohn's disease, and various cancers.

They also investigated whether any of the GWAS SNPs restore near-palindromes into perfect palindromes. Only about 5% of such restored palindromes were associated with disease, and some of them were located in genes already associated with multiple diseases, and so probably not the cause. So less than 5% of the created-perfect palindromes are associated with disease, whereas the mutated palindromes were 14 times more likely to be linked to disease. One interpretation of this is that there is some mechanism(s) which creates perfect palindromes, and as these degenerate they allow disease to enter (see theory of disease below). This is the opposite of what is expected from the modern synthesis.

We thus have two results. Firstly, palindromes are *symmetrical ordered patterns in the DNA* (most of which are too complex to have arisen by random processes within the known age of the Universe). Therefore they are not random. *Therefore, this is experimental evidence that the DNA which encodes them is not random*, and so there needs to be a source(s) of order. Secondly there is preliminary evidence that perfect palindromes are healthier than mutated ones. These results suggest that there are processes in nature which create ordered patterns.

When theory (the calculations above) and experiment (the DNA palindromes) agree like this, we do not have an ordinary biological fact, but a physics-grade fact. We calculated above that DNA could not have evolved by random processes, and the experimental evidence is that it did not in practice. *Therefore it is not random in origin.*

E. After the Modern Synthesis

It seems that not many scientists were aware of the above objective results, but Lima-de-Faria did and so he took a different approach.[27] However most biologists have become aware in other ways of the short-comings of the modern synthesis. It appears that evolution is more complex than previously thought and there are other factors at work, such as genetic plasticity; natural induction; epigenetics; niche construction; horizontal gene transfer; evolvability; and others. It appears that evolution is changing,[28] and in several different directions: the new biology beyond the modern synthesis;[29] postmodern synthesis;[30] the extended evolutionary synthesis;[31] to give a few examples.

In order to find a way through this confusion, we distinguish between the gentle evolution of species studied by biologists, from that sought by physicists, namely the evolution/development/creation of more complex living states from lifeless random matter. We need to understand the latter and find the true origins of complexity, if such mechanism(s) exist, because in the previous sections, we have shown that evolution could not have occurred by random means. Both theory and experiment require the existence of a source(s) of order, to create such high levels of order and to produce long DNA palindromes. *Therefore this rules out any minor adjustments to the modern synthesis.*

This brings us back to evolution. We now show that the (gentle) evolution (of biologists) is not a theory of life, in three ways. Firstly, we have shown above that random processes could not have given rise to replicating robots of any significant complexity nor living organisms within the known age of the Universe. So no system of evolution based upon random processes could create life, as we know it. If there is any doubt about this, consider the following. The human genome consists of 3.1 billion base pairs. Therefore the permutative complexity of the human genome is of order $N \simeq 4^{3,100,000,000} \simeq 10^{1,870,000,000}$ (i.e. 1 followed by 1.87 billion zeros), and this does not include the complexity of the food chain, which we depend upon. Living organisms are *so highly complex* that randomness cannot have given rise to them, even in 10^{500} universes.[32]

Secondly, we can understand this conceptually as follows. In Newton's theory of motion, velocity is the rate of change of position with time ($v = dx/dt$). This is called a "first order" effect. Acceleration is the rate of change of velocity ($a = dv/dt = d^2x/dt^2$), and this is a "second order" effect. The real problem with Darwin's theory of evolution is that he does not explain the first order effect (life), and tries to explain the second order effect (evolution) in terms of changes in the first order effect, *which he has no explanation for*. Furthermore, some of his followers try to

explain the first order effect (life) *in terms* of the second order effect (evolution, eg of replicators). This is circular reasoning. It seems highly likely that biological evolution will not be understood until there is a theory of life, and then it may not be important.

Thirdly the theory of evolution requires the existence of two states, the living and the non-living. Without these two states, natural selection is not possible. The former is allowed to evolve, but the latter cannot. However without the latter, the former could not. There is no explanation of the difference between the two states. *The theory just assumes that life exists.* So this is not a theory of life. Related to this is that the non-living state decays, whilst the living state (whilst healthy) does not. There is no explanation for this.

Before we present a possible physical source of order, we need to consider other theories of life.

V. WHAT IS LIFE?

It is easier to ask this question than to answer it, unless, of course, life is not an “it”. However, we need to penetrate to the deeper truth in order to create a new science of life to replace the modern synthesis. Furthermore we live in an age of robots starting to take on normally human activities, such as driving a car, conversing with humans (chatbots), and even writing essays for university exams. Is an information processing machine alive? Or is life more fundamental and so more important?

A. Theories of Life

There have been numerous attempts to explain life. We consider a few briefly here. In his review paper *What is Life? A Brief Historical Overview*,^[33] Lazcano puts these attempts into 12 categories. We list the titles of these categories here with a few (keywords) and some brief comments:

1. *The Body Electric* (Galvani - electricity, Schrödinger - quantum). Schrödinger’s approach was also from physics, but not electrical. We discuss his approach in more detail below.

2. *From Primordial Enzymes to Ancestral Nucleic Acids?* (genes) DNA plays a key role in hereditary phenomena, and this led to the molecularisation of biology. Molecular biology is discussed in a separate section below.

3. *Genes vs Protoplasm* (Muller vs Oparin, DNA vs metabolic flow). Muller believed life started with the appearance of the DNA molecule. However, Oparin thought it developed in a slow step-

wise evolutionary process, from some prebiotic soup. But how does something non-living “evolve”? Oparin also believed that the essence of life is metabolic flow - a special form of motion in matter. This brings us to the physics of the food chain - see below.

4. *Can Life be Defined?* (No, not in a way which can be generally agreed.) This is interesting. If one cannot define it, how can one determine what it is? Physicists generally are not interested in definitions, because they are just words. They are interested in the more abstract processes going on behind the phenomena observed. For example, perhaps it is not an “it”? This brings us back to the mind of the scientist - see below. These different definitions help explain the many different approaches to finding out what life is. Furthermore, there is the related problem of when life began, if it began at all, or if it ever stopped beginning.

5. *Autopoiesis and Living Systems* (metabolism, healing). Autopoiesis is the internal process of self-maintenance and self-generation, which is often linked to metabolism. However, viruses do not have a metabolism, so does this mean they are nonliving? Curiously few scientists do research into healing, which surely involves stimulating autopoiesis?

6. *The Primitive Soup and the Appearance of Life* (abiotic synthesis, prebiotic). Here is the idea of the synthesis of more complex substances in a prebiotic broth. Much of chemistry consists of synthesising (more complex) substances and so this is an approach which attracts chemists. They focus on how simple organic constituents were assembled into polymers and then into the first living entities, whilst ignoring the statistical impossibility of this without source(s) of order, and also the problem of when life begins, and the unity of the organism.

7. *Pyrite-Based life?* (Autocatalytic metabolic cycles.) Experiments show that ferrous sulphide in the presence of hydrogen sulphide (H_2S) is an efficient reducing agent, which can produce hydrogen and hence ammonia from nitrogen, but not much more.

8. *The Search for an RNA World* (ribozymes). Cells are based upon three interlinked parts, a membrane, DNA and protein enzymes. DNA genes can only replicate themselves with enzymes, whilst enzymes require instructions from DNA to make them. However, both DNA and enzymes depend upon a membrane to regulate and protect the inner state. One solution to this chicken-and-egg problem, is that the catalytic activity of RNA molecules may have led to alternative life forms based on ribozymes, before proteins and DNA genomes existed.[34, 35]

9. *Life and the Single, Lonely Molecule* (Primitive soup \neq RNA world). Four of the central reactions involved in protein biosynthesis are catalysed by ribozymes, which suggest they first appeared in the hypothetical RNA world. However, we lack a detailed scheme showing how to go from a primitive soup to the RNA world.

10. *Complexity and the Appearance of Life* (Complexity theory and self-organising systems). These are a number of different theories inspired, in part by computers and network theory, so they tend to be inanimate in origin. These are discussed in more detail in a section below.

11. *Towards a Darwinian Definition of Life* (unity, prebiotic soup. heterotrophic origin of life). Life evolves over time (physics), therefore the first living entities must have been self-sustaining with some form of genetic material, which evolved out of updated prebiotic soup.[36] Again DNA is too complex and this would not explain DNA palindromes.

12. *In conclusion* (Is life non-material? Genes and Darwinian evolution). Lazcano is against drawing a strict line between the nonliving and living states when considering the origin of life.

This is an exceedingly short summary of several complex subjects, and the reader who seeks more information is referred to Lazcano's paper.[33]

The most important point is that there is no consensus in this debate, and in fact there is no agreed definition of life. Does the problem come back to the brain of each individual scientist, their interests, different perceptions, subjects studied, facts, experiences, and possibly different beliefs? Or is it the problem of the evolution of the human brain? Has it evolved the same for everybody? Is it capable of understanding life? The human brain is an information processing device, and so it can be susceptible to entropy (randomness), just as computers are prone to bugs. The net effect is that some people may support one or more of these theories for different reasons.

Lazcano makes the observation that these theories fall into two categories: those which try to explain life in terms of physical phenomena (eg Galvani, Schrödinger), and those which involve some form of matter (molecules, biochemicals, Darwin's small pond), which form the majority. But in addition there are a series of theories of complex systems, which appear to have derived in part from computers and networks (e.g. the telephone network), that is from complex but inanimate systems. Whilst these theories involve self-organisation of matter, they are not chemistry in the normal sense. Furthermore they are based not on physics, but advanced mathematics, and are often in denial of physics.[37] We now investigate complexity theory in more detail.

B. Self-Organisation and Complex Systems

Complexity theory is applied to anything complicated such as business, economics, the stock market, the weather, complex networks, and to living organisms because they are also complex. Experts use a number of terms (jargon), such as *self-organisation*, *emergence*, *network theory*, *synergetics*, *collective behaviour*, *non-equilibrium phenomena*, to describe similar phenomena which

occur *at the edge of chaos*. We limit the discussion here to the work of Prigogine and Kauffman because they have both restricted their work mainly to biology and living organisms.

1. *Dissipative Structures*

Nicolis and Prigogine developed their theory of dissipative structures to explain self-organising phenomena such as the Belousov-Zhabotinsky reaction.[38] Basically a dissipative structure occurs when non-linear chemical reactions with feedback mechanisms, are coupled to dissipation to create a stable ordered state. Typically, raw materials and/or energy are brought in to drive the reaction and *entropy is pumped out so as to create order in the system*. Prigogine won the Nobel Prize for showing that a dissipative structure occurs in living organisms.[39] Whilst this is an interesting theory, it is not the main source of order in the living organisms for several reasons. For example, dissipative structures collapse if the supply of raw materials is interrupted, whilst living organisms tend to loose weight instead. (A human being can last up to about 40 days without food, but a dissipative structure is likely to collapse much more quickly.)

Another difficulty is that dissipative structures create order by excreting disorder. As a result they would, over time, be surrounded by more and more chaos, and the landscape would look like a wasteland. Coral reefs and tropical rain forests are teeming with life, and most organic matter is *recycled*, because living organisms start to decay when they become lifeless. *So there must be positive sources of order*. Furthermore, this is a classical (19th century) physics theory, which does not allow for the quantum mechanical properties of living organisms, e.g. the eye can detect single photons.[40] So whilst this is a serious attempt to explain the order and complexity of life, it fails to do so.

2. *Spontaneous Emergence*

Kauffman is a medical doctor, theoretical biologist, biophysicist and complex systems expert who has researched the origins of life on Earth. An important theme in his 700 page book *The Origins of Order*, is that self-organisation and the spontaneous emergence of order should be linked to natural selection, and incorporated into evolutionary theory.[41] He also proposes the self-organised emergence of self-catalysed networks of polymers, which become collectively self-reproducing, although initially lacking genes. It is true that there are many examples of self-organisation in biology, for example the self-assembly of biological membranes and of viral capsids,

and the auto-organisation of lipid molecules in bilayers, micelles, and liposomes. He gives additional examples. However, this is not proof that "self"-organisation occurs.

The problem is that this is biology, everything is very complicated, and other things could be going on, in particular there could be other (hidden) sources of order, which we do not know about. If one observes molecules self-organising, this does not prove that self-organisation occurs, because *one first has to prove that there is no process or mechanism, hidden or otherwise, which could have externally caused the assembly to come about.* And proving a negative is difficult.

One "solution" is to quote the second law of thermodynamics, namely that the entropy of a closed system tends to increase. However, physicists are so certain of this, that they never look for self-organising mechanisms or processes. Furthermore, if they do, and they find something, it is unlikely that anybody will believe them because it is theoretically impossible! There is a blind spot here, which is not helped by the way science is organised into physics, being the study of inanimate phenomena, and the life sciences being the study of animate systems.

Whilst this is a very serious book, deeply researched, its basic assumption (that evidence for self-organisation is proof of self-organisation) is flawed, because there may be hidden sources of order. There have been a number of additional criticisms of it. For example, Fox writes *The importance of energy as a driving impetus for organisation, as distinct from mere, and almost magical, self-organisation, is missed in Kauffman's exposition.*[42] Lazcano criticises the reliance on self-organisation without genes. Furthermore it seems unlikely that self-organisation, even if it leads to the formation of viable DNA, would lead to DNA palindromes noted above. In addition, it seems unlikely that a collection of chemicals, however well organised, is necessarily alive. Lazcano concurs.

But the real problem is that this weighty and seriously researched book has started to become an authority that "proves" that self-organisation is the source of complexity, if not actually of life. This is seriously misleading because no attempt has been made to reveal the (hidden) processes in nature, if any, which create the order. Without an equally serious search for such processes and proof of their non-existence, it is not "proof" of "self"-organisation.

C. Summary: What is Life?

Lazcano wrote about complex systems:

It is easy to recognise that the current attempts to explain the nature of life on the basis of complexity theory and self-assembly phenomena fall into a long and somewhat

erratic intellectual tradition that has led physicists to search for all encompassing laws that can be part of grand theory encompassing many, if not all, complex systems.[43] Unfortunately, complexity models have promised much but have delivered little.

The present author belongs to this "somewhat erratic intellectual tradition" of physicists, and takes seriously Lazcano's requirement of a relationship with actual biological phenomena. In his summation, Lazcano toys with the idea that life might be non-material, and then concludes that *life cannot be understood in the absence of genetic material and Darwinian evolution*. Unfortunately we have already shown above that this approach is contrary to the evidence, and so we will return to the physics approach below. Nevertheless, we think it only fair to investigate molecular biology more thoroughly, because it is such a well-developed science.

VI. MOLECULAR BIOLOGY AND INFORMATION

Molecular biology may not claim to be a theory of life, but its mainly unwritten assumption is that we are made of chemicals, so if we study these chemicals, we will understand life. There are problems with this. Firstly you are not made of chemicals because about 70% of the body is water, and up to 85% of parts of the brain consists of water. You may want to think about that.

Of course water is a chemical, but most chemists think of it as a solvent. The real biochemicals studied are the proteins, and other organic molecules. Water is there in the background, and is seemingly passive. However *if you moisten seeds, they will start to grow*. What chemical reaction causes seeds to sprout (and helps your brain to think)? Clearly water is of fundamental importance to life. In fact water is a very peculiar substance, and it is also studied by scientists, but often as a separate subject from biochemistry, which is unfortunate because the two are so closely linked.[44]

So are we made of chemicals if water is included? Not really because we are not made of a *random* collection of chemicals. Instead we are made from *very highly organised chemicals*. This is not semantics because even though our bodies are 70% water, it does not slosh around as in a plastic bag. Something is organising it (including the water). Is this due to chemistry alone, or is some physics involved?

Water molecules form about 30% by weight of active proteins.[45] Hydrogen bonds, which are only about 5% as strong as covalent bonds, play a key role in holding important biomolecules together.[46] For example DNA and haemoglobin molecules would not exist without hydrogen bonds, because they are held together by hydrogen bonds.[47] So we would not be here without the hydrogen bond, because these two molecules are essential for physical life. However, the

hydrogen bond also forms networks between the surrounding water molecules. Furthermore, the three dimensional structure of proteins, which is responsible for their function, is maintained in large part by hydrogen bonds.[48] In effect proteins are *no more rigid* than the surrounding water networks, because both are maintained by weak hydrogen bonds, which bend and rotate easily. Action and reaction are equal and opposite (Newton's third law of motion) and so biomolecules float and move in water a bit like seaweed, reacting to every subtle change in the water. Yet living organisms have form and structure. How? Why? Does this require something (presumably more physical) to organise the water?

One of the methods of biochemistry is to make ball-and-stick models of molecules to represent their structure. The problem is that atoms and molecules are not like this. In quantum mechanics, atoms are fuzzy and vibrating. Specifically more than 99.95% of the mass is concentrated in the nucleus, which is of order 10^{-5} of the radius of the atom. Less than 0.05% of the mass is in the electron cloud around the nucleus, which is approximately 99% empty space. Furthermore, the atoms are vibrating due to thermal agitation. So to represent molecules with ball-and-stick models *is seriously misleading*, because it implies that biochemicals are more rigid and solid than they really are. *To claim more precision than the data allows, is a serious error in science.* Karplus and McCammon have argued this has come about because X-ray crystallography yields time-averaged structures for proteins and other molecules, so that thermal and quantum fluctuations are hidden.[49] This is particularly a problem for the lock-and-key mechanism of enzyme action. In reality things are more dynamical, and could be completely different.

For example, Preparata and del Giudice have criticised the static picture of chemical bonds linking individual molecules together ("electrostatic meccano" or "erector set"), and replaced it with a dynamical interaction between groups of molecules spread over larger distances. This theory, known as coherent quantum electro-dynamics or CQED, is a new theory of condensed matter.[50] The hydrogen bonds in water make or break after a few picoseconds,[51] so that fluctuating EM fields are produced. The problem is that quantum mechanics ignores this, but QED does not and so produces different results. Do the hydrogen bonds in proteins also make and break like this? If so then the phenomena inside cells could be even more complex and different.

There is another aspect of biochemistry which is also very peculiar. Enzyme-catalysed reactions proceed with 100% yield of the target molecule: *there are no by-products*, although there may be waste products. However, if the same reactions are performed in a test tube with man-made catalysts, one or more by-products are nearly always produced and the yield is usually much less than 100%. Therefore intensive purification of the product is required at each step in the laboratory.

However in living organisms, enzymes are so specific, that the organism can carry out many different reactions simultaneously, *without producing useless by-products*, which would otherwise clog cells up and cause them to cease to function.[52] In other words, *biochemical reactions in cells are not random*. This agrees with our findings above, that proteins and DNA are not random. But how, why?

This is not normal chemistry. The reader will know these reactions are "catalysed" by enzymes, and that the "lock-and-key" mechanism makes them specific. But this is to confuse the classical and quantum paradigms. Furthermore, how did enzymes come into existence? And why are they so specific, when everything is fuzzy and vibrating at the molecular level, because of quantum mechanics and thermal motion (or is something regulating these?). Basically enzymes are like digital robots, which produce the target molecule when and where required. This is very peculiar.

Here is another example. Gold is notoriously resistant to corrosion, and can only be dissolved with difficulty in aqua regia. However, if one places gold leaf on someone's tongue, it just seems to dissolve and disappear! The body draws it in. Gold is legally allowed as a food additive in the US and the EU. What the mechanism for this is not clear, but it is not normal chemistry.

Thus biochemistry, despite all its successes, does not include water properly; it does not explain the absence of randomness in biochemical reactions; nor why biochemistry is so different from normal chemistry. Is this because molecular biology and biochemistry are circular reasoning, because they ignore everything else which is going on? Are chemists drawn into thinking they know and understand what is going on, because they can control it?

A. Szent-Györgyi

Another criticism of molecular biology comes from Szent-Györgyi who won the Nobel Prize for Medicine and Physiology in 1936 for elucidating some of the functions of vitamin C. In 1966 he wrote:[53] *In studying life, you keep diving from higher levels to lower ones until somewhere along the way, life fades out, leaving you empty handed. Molecules and electrons have no life.* In other words, matter is inanimate and does not explain life. He later wrote:[54]

That our body is composed of organs was discovered by the anatomists of the Renaissance. That these organs are composed of cells was discovered by the microscopists of the nineteenth century. That the cells are composed of molecules was established by the present biology, which is molecular biology.

Molecules are composed of atoms, and atoms of electrons and nuclei, which are composed of still smaller units. How far this subdivisibility of nature continues we do not know, but as far as biology is concerned we have reached the bottom with electrons... So in biology we are faced with four dimensions only: macroscopic, microscopic, molecular, and electronic. Biology has followed through as far as the molecular dimensions, but has failed to penetrate through into the electronic dimension.

What distinguishes the "animate" (alive) from the "inanimate" (not alive) is the subtle reactivity of living systems. Since the main bearers of life are proteins, *one would expect proteins to show similar subtle reactivity. They do not.* This gap between living and non-living has to be bridged.

Thus Szent-Györgyi concluded that molecular biology does not explain life. So he went on to develop a system of *sub-molecular biology* to explain the difference between living and non-living matter.[53] Despite physicists finding that the Observer collapses the wave function in quantum mechanical processes, submolecular biology has not taken off as much as it might have. Meanwhile, the computer industry has thrown up a new approach - information.

B. Information

Paul Nurse has suggested that information is life.[55] Certainly DNA is like the hard drive of a computer system with the coded instructions to make all the required proteins. Living organisms sense their environment and what is going on outside and inside them, and react accordingly, but this involves consciousness. Furthermore, the analogy is not perfect because, whilst normal computer software runs on the hardware, the software in a living organism *creates and organises* the hardware (i.e. the biomolecules, cells and organs). For example, the code in DNA is used to make the proteins and enzymes the organism is built from. Furthermore there are other problems.

Let us focus on cells. When a cell divides, hundreds of complex reactions work together to copy the DNA and create the new cell. When this happens correctly, the cell reproduces. However, it is not clear how this comes about. The 22,000 genes of a human being have a total length of 2 metres, but fit into the nucleus of a cell of diameter 6 microns. There the double helix has to be separated and copied. The pitch of DNA is about 3.5nm so this would require about 570 million rotations if done mechanically. There is still no agreed upon detailed mechanism for this. It is difficult to comprehend how it is done within the nucleus of a cell, with such precision.

Furthermore, most of the substances in a cell are proteins, or are constructed by proteins. For example a single yeast cell has over 40 million proteins in it. As a result there are a large number of biochemical reactions proceeding in the cell at the same time. If you could see it, it would appear to be seething with biochemical activities. So at any one time a cell contains many thousands of different reactions working to keep it alive. These processes occur on very short time scales. For example some enzymes catalyse thousands, even millions of reactions every second. Furthermore, they are extremely precise, even acting on individual atoms.

This analogy of computer software and hardware breaks down, because computer hardware is hardwired, and designed for the computer code to run on it. However, in a cell the (millions) of biochemicals can move around and 'rewire' the system at random. Furthermore, the biomolecules are subject to thermal motions and quantum fluctuations, and in addition there are water molecules moving at random. Yet a metabolic pathway can produce the target molecule with 100% yield and no byproducts. It is difficult to understand how the DNA molecule can control all these subsequent processes in 4D space time in an aquatic environment.

The problem is so serious that the term 'wetware' has been introduced.[56] However, a new word will not solve the problem of how these millions of biochemicals moving around at random in the cell, *are actually organised into a coherent whole*, which may even have a sense of purpose. Or is Nurse endowing "information" with some of the properties of consciousness?

The problem is even more complicated (you may not easily learn this from most biochemical sources), because these reactions are taking place mainly in water, whose molecules are moving due to thermal energies. (How does geometrical form develop out of this?) As a result there are constant disruptions by random processes similar to Brownian motion, which are exacerbated by the role of weak hydrogen bonds in proteins. Yet the biochemical reactions are not random! They occur in the correct sequence, without the production of by-products.

Furthermore, they occur on a time scale of a second or less, yet it is claimed that the whole process was set in motion and "tuned" by evolution which occurred millions or even billions of years ago. This is not causality. What happened millions or more years ago, cannot anticipate and correct random processes which occur in the current moment. And to believe otherwise is not science. The reality is there has to be some process(es) which create order and provides some kind of top-down organisation of the processes in the cell. Information alone cannot provide this, although it clearly has a role to play (provided it is not destroyed by the second law of thermodynamics). This requires some kind of unity which information alone cannot provide, because it is just a string of bits (or bases).

VII. THE MISSING PIECES

There are several pieces missing, including water, sources of order, unity, and possibly even life itself. The above approach of scientific research of taking living organisms apart (organs, cells, biochemicals) to see what they are made from, has failed. However, there is an explanation for this.

A. Unity

The physicist Niels Bohr, whose father was a physiologist, wrote that if you take a living organism apart to see how it works, it will die on you “*before it yields up its ultimate secret*”.[57] So whilst the approach of molecular biology is interesting, *it cannot penetrate the real inner secrets of life*. Furthermore, this suggests that the real secret of living organisms is their unity.

The point is that a random collection of chemicals does not have unity. If one tips a lorry load of bricks onto the ground, one does not have a house, just a random heap of bricks. To build a house, one needs a plan and one has to proceed methodically, starting with the foundations, which preferably are not on water-logged ground. Engineers know that if you want something to happen, then you have to make it happen. So most kinds of manufacturing process (eg for an airplane) have unified, often hierarchical control systems, regulating every detail, as things are built from the bottom up. So we need both a source of order and a source of unity, for living organisms to be built up in an orderly and coherent way. Such unified control systems must exist in living organisms. Epigenetics is an example of a higher level control system. Organising the 40 million proteins in a yeast cell requires a more complex control system. Homoeostasis with its control of many different variables, provides another example of this. This is particularly important for the immune system, which has to identify the unity of the organism, and distinguish it from everything else which is non-self. However, *unity cannot be provided by matter, because matter is particulate and so separate*.

B. Water and Heavy Water

Secondly, Szent-Györgyi was one of the minority of biochemists who also understand the importance of water for life.[58] A physicist’s approach to understanding the importance of water in living organism, is to compare the effects of water with those of heavy water. Heavy water has the same electron structure and the same molecular shape. It has two heavy hydrogen atoms and one

oxygen atom (D_2O), like ordinary water (H_2O). The heavy hydrogen atoms each have one electron going round a nucleus containing one proton, just like ordinary hydrogen. The only difference is that each heavy hydrogen atom (deuterium) has an extra neutron right at the centre, in the nucleus, which makes heavy water 11% denser than ordinary water. But it does not change the electronic structure, nor most of its outer chemical properties. Heavy water is clear and looks the same, smells the same, even tastes the same as ordinary water. *However it is poisonous.*

For example, various aquatic creatures died when placed in heavy water (of 92% concentration) within a few hours: tadpoles within one hour; a common aquarium fish within two hours; flatworms in three hours; and protozoa in 48 hours.[59] Rats given only heavy water to drink, *will not drink it and prefer to die of thirst.* The life-span of goldfish was reduced from years to 10 days by 40% heavy water. In fact, when goldfish were placed in 50% heavy water, *they tried to escape by jumping out!*[60]

The most conclusive experiment is with seeds. We mentioned above that if you moisten fertile seeds with normal water, they will germinate. However, *if you moisten them with heavy water, they will not sprout!* This was first demonstrated by Lewis in 1933.[61] This is clear evidence *that life is not chemical, but physical*, because the extra neutron is *electrically neutral*. It therefore does not interact with the electrons, *and so has no normal chemical effects*. Instead, its effects are *mechanical*. It increases the mass of the nucleus which increases its inertia and causes it *to vibrate at a lower rate*, and this is sufficient to make heavy water poisonous and stop seeds sprouting. This is clear evidence that life is not chemical *but physical in origin*, as Szent-Györgyi concluded in a different way.

C. Discussion

We have started to reach some challenging conclusions, that life could not have evolved by random mutations, and did not because DNA is not random. Furthermore, that evolution is not a theory of life, as Darwin recognised. Nor does biochemistry explain the differences between living and non-living matter. In fact the reasoning of biochemists is circular because they leave out anything which does not support their paradigm. The evidence is that life is very orderly, very highly so, and therefore there must be source(s) of order in nature, because what happened billions of years ago cannot control the present moment. We now present the first step in understanding the source(s) of order for the food chain and metabolism.

VIII. THE PHYSICS OF THE FOOD CHAIN

A few physicists have been studying the physics of the food chain. This started with Schrödinger's book *What is Life?*.^[62] He asked why it is that adults eat, since they do not need extra nitrogen atoms when they are fully grown. Nor do they need to replace one with another, because one nitrogen atom is as good as another. He concluded that the reason they eat is *to absorb the order in the food*, which physicists refer to as “negative entropy” (somewhat unfortunately since it is so positive). He reasoned that the food chain is a flow of negative entropy (i.e. order and information).

Before we continue, it will help some readers if we explain how physicists came to use this term “entropy”. In 1850 Rudolph Clausius stated the principle that *heat cannot pass from a cold to a hot body*. In 1851 William Thomson (later Lord Kelvin) put it differently: *there is always dissipated heat*. In 1865, Clausius noted that there are two types of energy: that which is *available*, and that *unavailable*. He called this inaccessible energy “entropy”. Thomson wanted to call the *available* energy “entropy”, and had he prevailed, the food chain would have contained ‘*positive entropy*. However that usage was not adopted. In the 1870s Ludwig Boltzmann was studying the statistical properties of bulk matter and showed that *entropy is a measure of randomness*. Order is the opposite of randomness, and so “negative entropy” or “negentropy” is used as a measure of information or order. This is how this negative term became applied to something so useful and positive.

So a more positive term would be helpful. For example, “gentropy” where the “g” comes from “neg”, but with the connotation of “good entropy”. In the absence of a consensus, we use “order” for “negative entropy” (i.e. ordered patterns, form, structure, information), and randomness for entropy (unavailable energy).

In its modern form, the second law of thermodynamics states *that entropy (randomness) tends to increase* (at least for irreversible processes, such as occur in bulk matter). This law is absolute in physics, so that it is considered to be certain that it cannot be reversed - but see below. In fact it is thought to lead to the “heat death” of the Universe, which results in the Universe degenerating to a state of total randomness. The problem is that *the highly ordered states of matter in living organisms*, apparently violate this principle, as does Schrödinger's theory of the food chain. Yet both exist, so what is the explanation?

The real problem is to explain where the order in the food chain comes from in the first place. How does order enter the food chain? Specifically, how does nature violate the second law of

thermodynamics, even though physicists are convinced this is impossible? A partial solution to this comes from a simple physics theory by Brittin and Gamow.

A. Brittin and Gamow's Theory

We now show that the sun's radiation is the source of order for the food chain. The sun's radiation consists of high temperature photons coming from the surface at $T_s \simeq 6,000^\circ \text{ K}$, which spreads out in space and becomes diluted. By the time it reaches the earth's surface, its energy density corresponds to a temperature of the earth ($T_e \simeq 300^\circ \text{ K}$), so these photons are not in thermodynamic equilibrium.

Brittin and Gamow use the quantum theory of radiation to show that the net entropy change on the earth's surface is:[63]

$$\Delta S = \Delta S_s - \Delta S_e = \frac{4}{3} \Delta Q \left(\frac{1}{T_s} - \frac{1}{T_e} \right) \quad (2)$$

This equation says that the entropy change at the earth's surface is equal to entropy coming in from the sun minus that being radiated away from the earth into empty space. This is *negative* because $T_s > T_e$, which means that order can build up on the earth's surface. The point is that the temperature of the earth's surface remains constant, if we ignore seasonal variations. Therefore all the heat coming from the sun (ΔQ), must find its way back into space ($-\Delta Q$). The main difference is that it is radiated away by maybe 10 to 20 as many low energy photons characteristic of the temperature of the earth's surface. These low energy photons go out into space in all different directions, and carry away more randomness than came from the sun, as shown in figure 1. Thus the entropy coming from the sun is less than that being carried away into empty space. *So the entropy at the earth's surface is reduced.*

The authors argue that this is not contrary to the second law of thermodynamics, because it is simply due to the temperature gradient $T_s > T_e > T_{\text{space}}$, which appears to be correct. However, there is a hidden complication.

This mechanism enables order (negative entropy) to build up on the earth's surface, *provided it can be stored*, because according to the second law it should dissipate. They calculate that photosynthesis has an efficiency of about 10% for capturing this negative entropy (order) and storing it.

This could provide the order for plants to build themselves up and be food for the metabolism of other organisms. However, metabolism is more complicated than this because it not only involves

FIG. 1: Radiation leaves the sun at about 6,000° K and arrives at the earth's surface, which is only about 300°K. In order to maintain its average temperature, the earth radiates this energy away using more low energy photons characteristic of its temperature. It radiates these in different directions, and they carry away more randomness (entropy), than comes from the sun. As a result order can build up on the earth's surface, provided it can be stored.

the ingestion of order, but also the excretion of randomness in wastes. Prigogine worked out the principles of this in 1945.[64] He realised that by ingesting order in its food and excreting disorder in its wastes, an organism can, in principle, overcome disorder produced internally and maintain itself in an ordered state. Thus Prigogine extended Schrödinger, Brittin and Gamow's theory to include metabolism.

We can also introduce a theory of disease here. Living organisms are complex, and, according to the above theory, are organised around a metabolism which ingests order and excretes disorder in waste products, so as to maintain their internal order. We suggest that disease is a breakdown in this process, which allows internal disorder to increase. Given that the food chain is a source of negentropy, it is possible that by ingesting sources of order (e.g. herbs) not normally present in

the diet, one can correct disease. This explains herbal medicine. This is supported by the finding above that imperfect palindromes with a single mutation are more strongly linked to disease, than palindromes which have been made perfect by the mutation.[24]

The advantage of this theory by Brittin and Gamow, is that it provides a source of order for the food chain, contrary to the second law of thermodynamics, which no physicist has refuted. *This is a very big advantage.* The disadvantage is that it is not a purely physical theory, at least not in its present form, because it relies upon plants (and hence biochemistry) to capture and store the negentropy (order). The question then is, what happened before photosynthesis had evolved/developed?

There are two possibilities: either photosynthesis developed by random processes (or otherwise emerged) from prebiotic soup to capture this negative entropy, or *there is some physical mechanism for capturing and storing it*, and so facilitates the formation of more complex states. The formula for Chlorophyll A is ($C_{55}H_{72}MgN_4O_5$) and that for Chlorophyll B is ($C_{55}H_{70}MgN_4O_6$). The main components are two atoms C and H, so the number of permutations is at least: $N \simeq 2^{55} \simeq 10^{16}$). If the initial structure changes every 10^{-8} seconds, then a chlorophyll molecule could in principle form in as little as $t \simeq 10$ years. There is the microscopic time selection window of 10^{-8} seconds during which the correct molecule has to stop evolving. But assuming that somehow this can be overcome (a big assumption), it is possible that photosynthesis evolved by random processes, and then continued to capture the order coming from sunlight to build up more complex organisms.

B. Discussion

A non-physicist reading this may think that sunlight is just another source of energy, like hydrothermal vents (which we do not discuss, nor chemosynthesis). However this energy from sunlight is not violent and destructive, like dynamite, although it does raise entropy levels a bit as it comes in. The keypoint is that it is the flow of energy in, and then out into the environment and eventually into outer space, which lowers entropy levels and is gentle and ordering. It's ability to create order is so important. Furthermore, life seeks it out and is drawn to it.

Throughout the above text we have presented considerable evidence that life is not random nor chemical in origin, but appears to be physical in origin. We have even shown above that there is a physical source of order produced by sunlight. However, we have also shown that it is plausible that photosynthesis evolved by random chemical processes to tap into this physical source of order. So which is it? Are living organisms chemical in origin, or physical in origin?

There are two possibilities: either there is no physical mechanism(s) for capturing and storing the order coming from the sun (as most physicists would expect), in which case life is chemical in origin. Or if there is a physical mechanism for capturing and storing this order (negentropy), then life is physical in origin, because highly ordered states could build up before chemical life developed. The latter is highly unlikely, and so life would be chemical in origin. However, it is important to investigate this physics and demonstrate its non-existence, so that the chemical origins of life are not an assumption, but a proven fact.

IX. CONCLUSIONS

Darwin himself did not claim that his theory was a theory of life, just of evolution. But some followers of the modern synthesis think it is a theory of life. However, calculations show that living organisms are so complex that even simple proteins could not have evolved by random processes within the known age of the universe. Furthermore, *there is experimental evidence that DNA is not random, because it contains palindromes, which are mirror-symmetric. Therefore it did not evolve by random processes.* When calculations and experiment agree like this, it becomes a physics-grade fact: namely that *randomness does not explain life.* Therefore Darwin was right. (His theory is of evolution, not of life.) It is the modern synthesis which is failing, as others have concluded in different ways. If living organisms are not random in origin, then we need a source(s) of order.

The method of taking living organisms apart to see how they work, has led (via anatomy and cells) to molecular biology. Szent-Györgyi has noted that it does not explain life because proteins, the basic molecular constituents of cells, have subtle reactivity inside living cells, but do not have that subtle reactivity outside cells - *they are not alive*, nor are other molecules or electrons. Therefore he argued, life must originate at a deeper, sub-molecular (i.e. physical) level. However, the material approach of molecular biology ignores water, which in fact is critical for life. Not only do living organisms consist mainly of water, but it stimulates seeds to grow and is essential for life in so many ways.

Water is a complex substance with many strange properties. Some scientists see it as the matrix of life.[58] However, it cannot be the source of order, because water molecules move at random as a result of thermal energy. So if there is a source of order, it must come from a *deeper, physical level.* This is supported by experiments with heavy water, which is poisonous and stops seeds from sprouting. The main difference between H_2O and D_2O is physical (i.e. the neutron in the heavy hydrogen nucleus), and so this is also evidence that *life is physical*, at least in origin.

Therefore the picture we are building up is that there are four levels of life: in addition to the macroscopic, microscopic and molecular levels, there is also water. Furthermore, there may be a deeper fifth level where physics creates order and unity.

The geometries of life (eg fractal) and the symmetries (eg left-right, rotational) provide additional evidence that living organisms are not random. Therefore there must be some mechanism(s) for creating order out of randomness.

We present the beginnings of a physical theory of the food chain, developed separately by Schrödinger, Prigogine, and Brittin and Gamow. In this theory, order is created by sunlight shining on the earth's surface, and by the excess heat radiated away into empty space. Some of this order is captured and stored by photosynthesis. But what happened before photosynthesis developed? Either chlorophyll developed by random chemical processes, possibly from prebiotic soup, OR there is some (inanimate) mechanism in physics for storing the order produced by sunlight, to facilitate the generation of more complex ordered states, eventually leading to chlorophyll. We argue that if such a storage mechanism exists then life is physical, if not then it is chemical in origin.

The order captured by photosynthesis then flows through the food chain to other organisms, who lower their entropy levels by ingesting order (in food) and excreting disorder (in wastes). This opens up new ways of studying living organisms, *by helping them build up more highly ordered states*. This is the opposite of taking them apart to see how they work, which Niels Bohr pointed out does not work because the organisms will die on you before they yield up their ultimate secret. In fact this suggests that their ultimate secret is their unity. So by stimulating the flow of negative entropy (order) into organisms, it may be possible to understand better their unity.

Einstein once said *The most incomprehensible thing about the Universe is that it is comprehensible*.^[65] That we have understood so much of the Universe suggests that our living brains are not a random collection of chemicals. The next step is to try to understand life (even if we can never comprehend the ability to comprehend), what it is and how it creates order.

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XI. STATEMENTS AND DECLARATIONS

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